

An Efficient Approach to Design a Reversible Fault Tolerant Programmable Array Logic

Md. Solaiman Mia^{1*} and Hafiz Md. Hasan Babu²

¹ *Department of Computer Science and Engineering, Hamdard University Bangladesh*

² *Department of Computer Science and Engineering, University of Dhaka, Dhaka-1000, Bangladesh*

**Email: solaimanducse@yahoo.com*

Abstract

Reversible circuits have applications in digital signal processing, computer graphics and cryptography. They are also a fundamental requirement in the field of quantum computation. We investigate the synthesis of reversible circuits that employ a minimum number of gates and contain no redundant input-output line pairs. In this paper, we have proposed a structure which constructs Reversible Programmable Array Logic (RPAL) as well as the RPAL is Fault Tolerant. An algorithm has been proposed to reduce total number of gates and garbage outputs in the AND plane of a RPAL. We compare the existing AND plane of Reversible Programmable Logic Array (RPLA) with the proposed one using benchmark functions. Our proposed design can realize ESOP (Exclusive Sum-of-Products) operations in terms of multi-output functions by using minimum number of gates, garbage outputs and quantum costs. In our design, we have used fault tolerant FRG (Fredkin Gate) and F2G (Feynman Double Gate) for making our RPAL Fault Tolerant. We have also proposed a fault tolerant design for RPAL in the OR plane with the minimum number of gates, garbage outputs and quantum costs. A Reversible Gate named FEG (Feynman Extension Gate) is also proposed to show the compactness of the proposed OR plane.

Keyword: Reversible Logic, Reversible Gate, Garbage Output, Quantum Cost, Programmable Array Logic.

1. INTRODUCTION

In the past few decades, reversible logic has become one of the most promising research areas. In modern technologies, power dissipation is an important issue and overheating is a serious concern for both manufacturer and consumer. When information loss occurs, energy is also lost. It happens when an input cannot recover its output and it has been proved by Landauer [1]. He also expressed that, if a bit of information is lost, then $KT \ln 2$ joules of heat generate; where K is Boltzman's Constant of 1.38×10^{-23} J/K and T is absolute temperature. To reduce energy waste, reversible circuit can be used and Bennet showed it [2]. Reversible logic follows one to one mapping system followed by input number and output number remains equal. Here no information loss and no energy dissipation occur. Miller proved that, if the number of gate increased, then it is not a good metric of optimization [3]. But reversible computing dissipates zero energy in terms of information loss and also it can detect errors of circuit by keeping unique input output mapping.

For error detection in digital systems, parity checking is one of the oldest, as well as one of the most widely used methods. Detection of faults generated in a circuit can be done by using parity-preserving reversible logic gates. The feasibility of the parity-preserving approach in the design of reversible logic circuits was demonstrated by B. Parhami [4] with examples of adder circuits. In this research, a modified HCG in which the parity of the outputs matches with that of the inputs is proposed. This can be used along with other parity preserving reversible logic gates to generate the parity preserved/fault tolerant hamming code. Parity preserving characteristic of such gates allows the detection of single fault generated in the circuit at the circuit's primary outputs in reversible logic design.

Fleisher and Maissel [5] introduced array logic based on AND, OR and NOT synthesis to implement SOP (Sum-of-Products) or POS (Product-of-Sums), whereas reversible logic prefers EX-OR operation as well as ESOP synthesis. ESOP synthesis gives out better result than SOP realization where many useful methods are proposed for minimizing multi-output Boolean functions into ESOP form. Cascade realization of reversible functions and garbage minimization technique is proposed in [6]. Programmable Logic Array (PLA) and Programmable Array Logic (PAL) have same design of AND plane and OR plane. The main difference is that, in PLA, both planes remain programmable, whereas in PAL, AND plane remains programmable and OR plane remains fixed. The generalized structure of Reversible PLA was first proposed in [7] based on ESOP realization of multi-output functions. In this paper, we have shown a novel design of a Reversible Fault Tolerant PAL and we also make comparison with the existing Reversible Fault Tolerant PLA.

The paper is organized as follows: Section 2 describes background studies on the architecture of Programmable Array Logic, the classic objects of reversible logic theory, fault tolerant and finally, quantum realization of reversible logic are defined. The existing and proposed works of reversible logic synthesis to develop reversible fault tolerant PAL is shown in Sections 3 and 4, respectively. Each proposed component is compared with existing one to prove the supremacy of the propounded circuit. Our proposed design is compared using benchmark functions in Section 5. Finally, a brief conclusion along with the goal of offering a new perspective on our proposed Reversible Fault Tolerant Programmable Array Logic is given in Section 6.

2. BACKGROUND STUDY

In a strictly reversible system, no information is allowed to be erased. Again reversible computing is enhanced from various fields like fault tolerant, quantum computing, online testability etc., where fault tolerant detects and corrects error. So, fault tolerant reversible logic can be used to handle error in most prominent computing design. In this section, some terms and definitions essential for basic understanding in PAL and reversible logic are discussed.

2.1 Programmable Array Logic

An elegant solution to the mapping of irregular combinational logic functions into regular structure is provided by the PAL [8]. The PAL provides the designer with a systematic and regular way of implementing multiple-output functions of n variables in SOP form. The general arrangement of a PAL is given as Fig. 1 and it may be seen to consists of a programmable one level AND and another level fixed OR structure.

Fig. 1: Structure of PAL.

Clearly, the structure is regular and may be expanded in any of its dimensions: the number of input variables, the number of product (AND terms), and the number of output functions (OR terms). It will also be noted that, if there are v input variables, for complete generality, each of the product forming AND gates must have v inputs, and if there are p product terms, each output OR gate must have p inputs.

2.2 Reversible Gate

Reversible logic has unique mapping between input and output bit pattern. A unit logic entity is represented as gate. The gates or circuits that do not lose information are called reversible [2] gates or circuits.

Definition 1: A reversible circuit is such a circuit in which the number of input and the number of output is equal. And of course, there is one to one mapping between input and output vectors.

Let's consider the gate shown in Fig. 2. According to the definition, the gate is a reversible gate, because it has k number of inputs and k number of outputs and the gate is known as $k \times k$ Reversible Gate. Without the NOT gate, classical logic gates are called irreversible, since they cannot determine the input vector states from the output vector states uniquely.

Fig. 2: A $k \times k$ Reversible Gate.

Example 1: There can be any number of dimensions for a reversible gate, but lower dimension is always preferable for designing efficient circuits. The popular reversible gates are Feynman Gate (FG) [9], Toffoli Gate (TG) [10], Peres Gate (PG) [11], Fredkin Gate (FRG) [12], Feynman Double Gate (F2G) [4] and New Fault Tolerant (NFT) [13] which are shown in Fig. 3.

Fig. 3: Popular Reversible Gates.

2.3 Garbage Outputs

Every gate's output that is not used as input to other gate or as a primary output is called garbage output. The unutilized outputs from a gate are called *garbage*. Heavy price is paid off for every garbage output. So, it should always keep in mind that, the less number of garbage is quite good for any circuit design.

Example 2: In the Fig. 4, the garbage bit of a gate is shown. Here, **A** is the garbage bit.

Fig. 4: Garbage Bit.

2.4 Fault Tolerant Procedure: Parity Preserving

There are some causes of circuitry violation. Bit error is one of them. Reversible circuit is able to espouse same parity between input-output bit patterns to provide fault tolerance facility.

2.5 Fault Tolerant Gate

Parity Preserving is a property of reversible logic, where every mapped input and output of a gate preserves same parity: odd or even. Parity preserving is only one method in fault tolerant reversible logic [14].

Definition 2: A reversible gate is fault tolerant which constantly preserves same parity between input and output.

Example 3: Generally, 1×1 and 2×2 gates are not assumed as fault tolerant. F2G, FRG and NFT gates are 3×3 and MIG is 4×4 fault tolerant gates.

2.6 Reversible Quantum Computing

Quantum theory is a gigantic research field deeply related to crucial applications as DNA technologies, nanotechnologies and optical computing etc. Reversible quantum logic plays an important role in quantum computing.

Definition 3: The quantum cost of a circuit is the total number of 2×2 quantum primitives are used to realize corresponding quantum circuit. Basically, the quantum primitives are matrix operations, which are applied on qubits state.

Example 4: The cost of all 2×2 gates are same and it is 1 and 0 for 1×1 [15]. Every circuit can be constructed from those 1×1 and 2×2 quantum primitives and the cost of circuit is the total sum of used 2×2 gates [16].

3. EXISTING REVERSIBLE FAULT TOLERANT PROGRAMMABLE LOGIC ARRAY

For recovering the error of reversible circuits, fault tolerant circuit is highly needed. The conversion of the whole non preserving world into fault tolerant will be better if it is started from basic level by realizing popular gates into fault tolerant fashion.

PLA allows SOP for implementing *Boolean* functions. The typical implementation consists of input buffers, the programmable AND matrix followed by the fixed OR matrix, and output buffers.

Definition 4: PLA consists of two planes: the first one is programmable AND plane and the second one is fixed OR plane known as AND-OR PLA. When the second plane works as EX-OR, then it is called AND-EXOR PLA [7].

PLA and PAL is almost same in architectural design. The PLA has also two planes as AND and OR plane. But the difference between PLA and PAL is: the OR plane of PLA is also programmable as AND plane, but the OR plane of PAL is fixed and the AND plane is programmable.

Since the AND part of PLA and PAL is programmable, we want to make such a design which is fault tolerant as well as minimized in the number of gates, garbage outputs and quantum cost. Before that, we mention here the existing works of PLA.

The beginning work of irreversible PLA is first designed as reversible PLA [7]. Since, it was the first design of reversible PLA, it required more number of gates, garbage outputs and quantum cost. Then, another work is done with reversible PLA for minimizing the total number of gates, garbage outputs and quantum cost [17]. These two designs were not fault tolerant. Finally, the design of reversible fault tolerant PLA is shown in [18].

The AND plane of existing reversible fault tolerant PLA is designed for some multi-output ESOP functions. Assume the functions are:

$$F1 = AC \oplus A'B'C$$

$$F2 = AB' \oplus AB'C$$

$$F3 = AB' \oplus AB'C \oplus BC'$$

$$F4 = AC$$

$$F5 = AB' \oplus AC \oplus BC'$$

The products of these functions are:

$$AC, AB', BC', AB'C, A'B'C$$

Definition 5: Frequency of a product is the total number of output functions, which will use this product. The Table 1 shows the frequencies of all products of multi-output functions {F1, F2, F3, F4, F5}.

Example 5: Table 1 shows that, the frequency of AC is 3 and A'B'C is 1.

Table 1: Frequency of Products

Products	Functions					Frequency of Products
	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	
AB'		x	x		x	3
AB'C		x	x			2
AC	x			x	x	3
BC'			x		x	2
A'B'C	x					1

Definition 6: Number of products of a function is the total number of products that are used to realize the function in ESOP form.

Example 6: The number of products of the function F1 is 2, because two products are required to realize the function F1 in ESOP form. Table 2 shows the number of products of each function individually.

Table 2: Number of Products

Functions	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5
Number of Products	2	2	3	1	3

Now, we give different representations of FRG and F2G in Fig. 5, which is used in existing design of reversible fault tolerant PLA [18] as well as we will use in our proposed design.

Fig. 5: Different Gate Representations of Fredkin Gate.

4. PROPOSED REVERSIBLE FAULT TOLERANT PAL

The existing design of PAL is not reversible as well as not fault tolerant. Our work combines several ideas to present the construction of reversible fault tolerant PAL for multi-output functions by introducing new structure based on F2G and FRG gates, heuristic algorithm for proposed reversible fault tolerant PAL, ordering of functions as well as ordering of products, optimization of EXOR plane and AND plane minimization in terms of products.

In our proposed design, we want to make the reversible PAL as fault tolerant. Since, the AND plane of PLA and PAL is programmable, our proposed algorithm will minimize the number of gates, garbage outputs and quantum cost as compared to previous one [18].

4.1 Proposed Design of AND Plane of Reversible Fault Tolerant PAL

As mentioned earlier, PAL has two planes: AND plane and EX-OR plane. In our proposed design, we use two fault tolerant gates: F2G and FRG for designing fault tolerant PAL. F2G is used for copy and complement the gate, and FRG is used for ANDing the inputs as required outputs.

We use the functions described as the existing design of reversible fault tolerant PLA uses. We will design such a circuit which will decrease the total number of gates, garbage outputs and quantum cost. With our proposed work, at first we sort the min-terms by the number of frequencies to decreased order. As a result, when the larger number of functions is copied or complemented, the lower number of functions is automatically generated.

When we do the AND operation using FRG, we take the inputs as two bits. So, for input **A** and **B**, there may be one of four conditions: **AB**, **AB'**, **A'B**, **A'B'**. If there exist another input along these terms, then the rest part of the input must have only one of the two forms: **(The previous form) . C** or **(The previous form) . C'**, if another input is **C**. The other inputs follow the same rule. This kind of operation will decrease the AND operation and thus will decrease the total number of gates, garbage outputs and quantum cost.

However, the normal design includes all the combination of inputs, that's why our proposed design is better than existing design [18].

We follow an algorithm for designing the AND plane of our proposed reversible fault tolerant PAL. The algorithm is given in Algorithm 1. Here, F2G and FRG are used for different combinations. In our proposed design, we also use the gates 1, 2 and 3 which are shown in Fig. 5. Our proposed AND plane design of reversible fault tolerant PAL is given in Fig. 6.

Algorithm 1 Algorithm for designing the AND plane of our proposed reversible fault tolerant PAL

1. START

- a. Sort Min-terms
- b. $TG := 0$ [$TG =$ Total Number of Gates]
- c. Put all literals into the Stack
- d. **Repeat** Step 1.d.i for each ordered Product (P_i)
 - i. **if** Product (P_i) is the single literal **then**
 1. Apply F2G Gate
 2. Increment Number of Gates
 3. Update Stack
 - ii. **End if**
 - iii. **else**
 1. **if** Two literals are Complemented **then**

- a. Apply F2G and FRG Gates
 - b. Increment Number of Gates
 - c. Update Stack
 2. **End if**
 3. **if** Two literals are in Normal Form **then**
 - a. Apply F2G and FRG Gates
 - b. Increment Number of Gates
 - c. Update Stack
 4. **End if**
 5. **if** One literal is Complemented and Another is in Normal Form **then**
 - a. Apply F2G and FRG Gates
 - b. Increment Number of Gates
 - c. Update Stack
 6. **End if**
 - iv. **End if**
 - e. **End Repeat**
- 2. END**
-

Fig. 6: Proposed Design of AND Plane of Reversible Fault Tolerant PAL.

Table 3: Comparison of Efficiency Parameters between Proposed and Existing Designs of AND plane of Reversible Fault Tolerant PAL

	Total Gates	Garbage Outputs	Quantum Cost
Existing [18]	10	11	41
Proposed	9	9	39

In Table 3, we have shown that, for some assuming functions, our proposed design is quite good, since it requires less number of reversible gates, garbage outputs and quantum cost.

4.2 Proposed Design of OR Plane of Reversible Fault Tolerant PAL

The OR plane of PAL is not programmable. So, when designing, we keep in mind that, we cannot change the pattern of OR plane's input from outside world. The OR plane is fixed. The output from AND plane of PAL is directly used to the input of EX-OR plane.

For designing the OR plane of our proposed reversible fault tolerant PAL, we use some other representations of F2G. The representations of F2G are shown in Fig. 7.

Fig. 7: Another Representation of F2G.

Our proposed OR plane design of reversible fault tolerant PAL is given in Fig. 8.

Fig. 8: Proposed Design of OR Plane of Reversible Fault Tolerant PAL.

4.3 Proposed Design of Minimized OR plane of a Reversible PAL

The previous subsections have shown the designs of reversible fault tolerant PAL. In the proposed design, for EX-OR plane, we used Feynman Double Gate (F2G). If we use some other gate in the place of F2G of EX-OR plane, then total number of gates, garbage outputs and quantum cost will be minimized compared to earlier design.

Now, we are going to propose a reversible gate called Feynman Extension Gate (FEG) here. With the help of this gate, we can EX-OR any number of inputs. The FEG input and output for N number of EX-OR literals is shown in Fig. 9.

Fig. 9: Feynman Extension Gate.

When working, If there exist more input literals of EX-OR plane, then the use of FEG will be the more flexible. Using FEG, if there is N inputs, then we use $E(N)$. For example, if there is 2 inputs, we use $E(2)$, if 3 inputs, we use $E(3)$ etc.

The algorithm for OR plane design of reversible PAL is given in Algorithm 2.

Algorithm 2 Algorithm for designing the OR plane of our proposed reversible fault tolerant PAL

1. START

- a. $TG := 0$ [$TG =$ Total Number of Gates]
- b. Calculate the Frequency of Min-terms

- c. Copy Corresponding Min-terms
 - i. (Suitable Feynman Extension Gate)
- d. Increment Number of Gates
- e. Apply XOR Operation
 - i. (Suitable Feynman Extension Gate)
- f. Increment Number of Gates

2. END

The proposed design of minimized EX-OR plane of our proposed reversible PAL is shown in Fig. 10.

Fig. 10: Proposed Design of EX-OR Plane of PAL.

From Fig. 10, for EX-ORing the input literals come from the AND plane of output functions F1, F2, F3, F4 and F5, we use only two E2 Gates and two E3 Gates. If we want to minimize the number of gates, garbage outputs and quantum cost, we can use this design, but it will not be fault tolerant. The comparison between using F2G and using FEG is given in Table 4.

Table 4: Comparison between F2G and FEG

Using F2G			Using FEG		
Gate	Garbage	Quantum Cost	Gate	Garbage	Quantum Cost
10	10	20	8	6	20

From the comparison shown in Table 4, it does not seem so effective to use FEG in the place of F2G. But, it will be very effective when total number of functions will increased, since with the help of FEG, we can EX-OR any number of literals.

5. COMPARATIVE STUDY

The existing design of reversible fault tolerant PLA [18] and our proposed design of reversible fault tolerant PAL has the same programmable AND plane. So, we compare the AND plane between existing [18] and our proposed design with the benchmark functions [19]. The comparison with the benchmark functions is given in Table 5.

Table 5: Comparison between Existing and Proposed AND plane Design with Benchmark Functions

Function	Proposed			Existing [18]		
	Gate	Garbage	Quantum Cost	Gate	Garbage	Quantum Cost
5xp1	99	97	423	110	104	472
9sym	346	289	1619	363	298	1704
adr1	1	2	5	3	4	9
adr2	12	16	39	14	20	46
adr3	39	41	156	43	47	176
apex1	2553	2253	12138	2615	2298	12448
apex3	1766	1540	8152	1778	1598	8212
b12	119	108	526	121	123	536
bw	65	69	268	66	64	273
clip	334	294	1532	358	303	1694
con1	24	26	96	27	33	111
cordic	10349	8879	50005	10424	8902	50380
duke2	649	598	3062	659	620	3112
e64	2143	2115	10523	2144	2180	10528
table3	1733	1419	8296	1768	1433	8471
table5	1772	1476	8482	1785	1493	8547
z9sym	346	289	1619	363	298	1704
25xp1	102	94	441	111	101	480
xor5	4	8	9	5	14	10
vag2	1741	1591	8309	1768	1616	8444
sao21	212	197	1003	221	207	1048
rd84	232	210	1022	246	218	1092
rd53	32	32	130	36	37	150
rd73	120	110	519	127	117	554
pdc	3020	2452	14329	3023	2468	14341

From Table 5, we can see that the proposed method is quite good, since it requires less number of reversible gates, garbage outputs and quantum cost than the existing ones. For example, existing design [18] for *rd84* circuit requires 246 reversible gates with 218 garbage outputs having 1092 quantum cost, whereas our proposed design requires 232 reversible gates with 210 garbage outputs having 1022 quantum cost.

6. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we have shown two kinds of reversible PAL: one is fault tolerant and another is non fault tolerant. Since, the AND plane is programmable as PLA, we have minimized the total number of gates, garbage outputs and quantum cost in our proposed design, which remains fault tolerant as well. When the full architecture of reversible PAL remains fault tolerant, EXOR plane is also fault tolerant and in this case, the reversible PAL requires more number of gates, garbage outputs and quantum cost. However, the proposed non fault tolerant reversible PAL requires less number of gates, garbage outputs and quantum cost. The reversible fault tolerant PAL is useful for designing the digital circuits easily. For example, large functions which have several variables can be easily implemented by using reversible fault tolerant PAL.

Our future work will include the realization and minimization of the quantum cost of the whole reversible circuit. Moreover, our future work will also include the design of compact reversible online testable programmable array logic.

REFERENCES

- [1] R. Landauer, "Irreversibility and Heat Generation in the Computational Process", IBM Journal of Research and Development, 1961, vol. 5, pp. 183-191.
- [2] C. H. Bennett, "Logical Reversibility of Computation", IBM Journal of Research and Development, November 1973, vol. 17, no. 6, pp. 525-532.
- [3] D. M. Miller, D. Maslov and G. W. Dueck, "A Transformation based Algorithm for Reversible Logic Synthesis", Proc. of the 40th Annual Design Automation Conference, June 2003, pp. 318-323.
- [4] B. Parhami, "Fault Tolerant Reversible Circuits", Proc. 40th Asilomar Conf. Signals, Systems, and Computers, Oct. 2006, Pacific Grove, CA.
- [5] H. Fleisher and L. I. Maissel, "An introduction to array logic", IBM Journal of Research and Development, March 1975, vol. 19, pp. 98-109.
- [6] D. Maslov and G. Dueck, "Reversible cascades with minimal garbage", IEEE Transactions on CAD, November 2004, vol. 23, no. 11, pp. 1497-1509.
- [7] A. R. Chowdhury, R. Nazmul, and H. M. H. Babu, "A new approach to synthesize multiple-output functions using reversible programmable logic arrays", IEEE 19th International Conference on VLSI Design, 2006, pp. 311-316, Hyderabad, India.
- [8] "Monolithic Memories announces: a revolution in logic design", Electronic Design, March 18, 1978, pp. 148B-148C.
- [9] R. Feynman, "Quantum Mechanical Computers", Optics News, 1985, vol. 11, pp. 11-20.
- [10] T. Toffoli, "Reversible Computing", Tech memo MIT/LCS/TM, 1980, vol. 151, pp. 11-20.
- [11] A. Peres, "Reversible Logic and Quantum Computers", American Physical Society, 1985, vol. 151, pp. 3266-3276.
- [12] E. Fredkin and T. Toffoli, "Conservative Logic", International Journal of Theoretical Physics, 1982, vol.21, pp. 219-253.
- [13] M. Haghparast and K. Navi, "A novel fault tolerant gate for nanotechnology based system", American Journal of Applied Sciences, 2008, vol. 5, no. 5, pp. 519-523.
- [14] M. S. Islam and Z. Begum, "Reversible logic synthesis of fault tolerant carry skip bcd adder", Bangladesh Academy of Science Journal, 2008, vol. 32, no. 2, pp. 193-200.
- [15] M. Perkowski, "A hierarchical approach to computer-aided design of quantum circuits", In 6th International Symposium on Representations and Methodology of Future Computing Technology, 2003, pp. 201-209.
- [16] W. N. N. Hung, X. Song, G. Yang, J. Yang and M. Perkowski, "Constructing online testable circuits using reversible logic", Computer Nature, 2004, pp. 838-841.
- [17] S. K. Mitra, L. Jamal and H. M. H. Babu, "Design and Minimization of Reversible Programmable Logic Arrays".
- [18] R. Rahman, L. Jamal and H. M. H. Babu, "Design of Reversible Fault Tolerant Programmable Logic Arrays with Vector Orientation", International Journal of Information and Communication Technology Research, 2011, pp. 337-342.
- [19] D. Maslov, Reversible Benchmarks [Online]. Available at <http://www.cs.uvic.ca/~dmaslov/>